

Principles, standards and criteria for quality science communication resources

The [European Competence Centre for Science Communication](#) is dedicated to supporting all actors from the research and innovation system and beyond, in their practice of science communication. *We are not alone* – a number of valuable resources, from handbooks to training materials have been produced by many institutions and individuals and are available in multiple languages.

The Competence Centre offers an online library (the “Scicomm Toolbox”), inviting the science communication community for their contribution to collect such resources. To ensure their quality and maximise their impact, a **set of principles, standards and criteria** (the “COALESCE PSCs”) were created. The PSCs are aimed both to resource creators, as a **self-reflection tool in their daily work**, as well as to users, as a **support tool** to select the most relevant and effective resources from those to be available in the Scicomm Toolbox.

The PSCs were defined based on theoretical literature, co-creation sessions with members of the COALESCE Community of Practice, and previous work by the SwafS-19 sister projects. The general approach was adapted from the principles, standards and indicators for outstanding open science communication, from [ENJOI](#).

Principles – *Concepts that serve as foundations for creating quality science communication resources –*

- **Scientific** – supports effective communication of scientific knowledge and the scientific process and the preparation and/or evaluation of its content followed scientific principles.. This might mean, for example, presenting evidence-based suggestions or using a scientific method to formulate these suggestions (e.g., using engagement workshops with stakeholders or using critical analysis of best practices).

- **Accessible** – aims to be as widely available and inclusive as possible. This might include, for example, being open access where possible in support of the [UNESCO Declaration for Open Science](#), publishing the resource in various languages or making it better accessible to people with impairments.
- **Responsible** – helps to uphold the ethical standards of science communication and support addressing current major challenges in science communication, such as, in fight against misinformation, increasing trust in science and reaching underrepresented or vulnerable groups. The resource contributes to advance the state of the art in science communication.

[These principles are aligned with the core principles of science communication – the resource promotes principles that have been defined for quality science communication in general (e.g., [ENJOI principles](#) or [QUEST quality indicators](#)) or for specific fields (e.g., [RETHINK quality indicators for online scicomm](#) or [NEWSERA indicators for citizen science projects](#)), and is supporting the competences that are considered key skills for scicomm (e.g., [Mercer-Mapstone & Kuchel, 2017](#); [Aurbach et al., 2019](#); [Bray, France & Gilbert, 2012](#))]

Standards – *Reference models that are used as general rules to measure quality and value of science communication resources* –

- **Contextualized and purposeful** – makes clear the contexts in which it is to be used, including, among others, medium, format, target group and science communication objective.
- **Audience-tailored** – uses language, tone and format that is appropriate for its target group.
- **Self-reflexive** – is aware of its strengths and weaknesses, collects user feedback, evaluates its impact and is updated when the context changes.

Criteria – *Measurable or observable factors, quantitative or qualitative, that help monitor the road towards the application of the Principles and Standards* –

General criteria are considered in **four dimensions**:

- **Technical quality**, including:
 - Production value – the professional level of making the resource clear, attractive and engaging (video or audio quality, visual design, etc)
 - Coherence – in style, format, structure, tone and language

- o Being up-to-date – keeps being current and relevant to ongoing developments, both regarding technical formats and content
- **Instructional quality**, including:
 - o Well-defined competences – defines the competences that the resource helps to develop
 - o Support – provides support in teaching or learning competencies (e.g., with pre-prepared training materials)
- **Scientific quality**, including:
 - o Context – clearly states for what context the resource was designed for
 - o Methodology – provides information how recommendations were produced
 - o Literature – engages with existing academic literature on science communication
- **Impact quality**, including:
 - o Feedback – collects user feedback and uses it to improve the resource
 - o Evaluation – provides guidelines on how to evaluate the outcomes or impact of the resource
 - o Inclusion – considers how the resource could support engagement with vulnerable or marginalised groups and promote diversity in science communication

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